

ÉCOLE POLYTECHNIQUE FÉDÉRALE DE LAUSANNE

Master Thesis in Life Sciences Engineering

Closed-loop modeling of sensorimotor feedback under epidural stimulation for spinal cord rehabilitation

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Dedication

Dedico questo lavoro al meraviglioso team del MINE laboratorio, in particolare a Anna, Chiara, Giuseppe, Katja, Laura, Marianna, Nicole, Simone, Veronica, e la team della baracchina, Benedetta, Mickael e Noemie e a tutti che hanno reso questa esperienza speciale. Mi hanno fatto sentire a casa fin dal primo giorno e parte della loro famiglia. Grazie a voi ho potuto scoprire la bellezza di Milano. Ogni momento trascorso insieme (nella baracca o nella città) è stato prezioso, e porterò sempre con me questi ricordi.

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Abstract

Spinal cord injury (SCI) disrupts both descending motor commands and ascending sensory signals, leading to severe motor impairments. Epidural electrical stimulation (EES) has emerged as a promising neuro-modulation therapy to restore motor function by activating spinal circuits and eliciting muscle contractions. However, how EES interacts with proprioceptive feedback in closed-loop conditions remains poorly understood.

Existing models typically treat EES-evoked muscle responses and proprioceptive feedback as two separate components: first afferent firing rates is computed from pre-recorded muscle data, and then muscle activation is estimated. In reality, however, neural activity and muscle responses continuously influence each other in a dynamic loop. In this thesis, we address this issue by presenting a closed-loop computational model of neuromuscular dynamics under EES, integrating spinal neuronal circuits (Brian2), a musculoskeletal model (OpenSim's Gait2392), and muscle-state sensory feedback. This framework enables us to investigate how the system's dynamics arise from the interactions between neurons and muscles under EES.

By varying motoneuron excitability, our model first reproduces both healthy motor behavior and pathological ankle clonus. The latter is characterized by synchronous motoneuron firing and 5 Hz ankle oscillations, in line with clinical observations. Unlike the clonus rhythm, our model predicts the emergence of a physiological alternation between tibialis anterior and medial gastrocnemius activity (2 Hz) with EES stimulation at spinal level S1, without invoking a central pattern generator. Critically, this rhythmic coordination relies on proprioceptive feedback; its removal leads to muscle co-activation or dominance. Furthermore, the model also shows that spatially imbalanced afferent recruitment promotes targeted muscle activation by altering sensory input patterns. Finally, we use the closed-loop model to dynamically adjust EES frequency at two different stimulation sites across movement phases. We demonstrate the benefit of spatiotemporal stimulation strategy to produce muscle activation patterns that more closely resemble natural locomotion.

These results highlight the importance of proprioception in EES-mediated motor control and demonstrate that targeted, adaptive stimulation can enable functional motor output without supra-spinal input. Our work lays the computational groundwork for designing personalized EES strategies to support neuro-rehabilitation in individuals with SCI.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Spinal cord injury

Spinal cord injuries (SCI) disrupt the bidirectional communication between the central and peripheral nervous systems, often resulting in long-term motor and sensory deficits. Nearly 70% of SCI patients suffer from pathological muscle co-contractions and spasticity, frequently accompanied by clinical signs such as patellar hyperreflexia and ankle clonus [41]. These impairments significantly impact quality of life and functional independence. Recovery is typically limited, as supraspinal fibers lack the ability to spontaneously regenerate and reestablish functional networks below the level of injury, underscoring the urgent need for effective therapeutic interventions.

1.2 Epidural electrical stimulation

In recent years, neuromodulation techniques such as epidural electrical stimulation (EES) have shown great promise in reducing abnormal neural activity [41] and restoring motor functions [42], following SCI. Strategic electrode placement targeting dorsal roots involved in leg and trunk movements enables individuals with severe SCI to stand, walk, cycle, swim, and control trunk movements within a single day of treatment [42].

The mechanisms underlying recovery mediated by EES remain incompletely understood. Experimental and computational studies indicate that EES primarily activates motoneurons trans-synaptically through excitation of large diameter afferent fibers, rather than by direct motoneuron depolarization [18, 10]. Moreover, residual supraspinal inputs might modulate motoneuron firing rates under EES and convert subthreshold EES-mediated excitatory postsynaptic potentials (EPSPs) into action potentials, depending on lesion severity [1]. Finally, several neuroplasticity mechanisms have been proposed, including potentiation of monosynaptic connections between proprioceptive afferents and motoneurons, reorganization of propriospinal circuits near the injury site, and enhanced spatiotemporal integration of sensory and motor signals within spinal interneuronal networks [14].

EES stimulation parameters critically determine therapeutic outcomes. Continuous EES, while enhancing muscle activity, poorly facilitates locomotion and disrupts proprioceptive feedback by antidromic collisions [48, 16]. In contrast, spatiotemporal EES protocols preserve

proprioceptive function and significantly improve walking capabilities [48]. Understanding the complex continuous interplay between stimulation parameters, proprioceptive feedback, neural circuits, motor and functional recovery is essential for maximizing EES therapeutic benefits in SCI rehabilitation.

1.3 State of the art

Computational models play a critical role in understanding the effect of EES. Among the most established approaches are finite element models (FEMs) of the spinal cord, which simulate the electric fields generated by EES based on the quasi-static approximation of Maxwell’s equations [10, 18]. These models are typically coupled with anatomically realistic cable models of neural structures, allowing for predictions of axonal recruitment and resulting motor responses. At the circuit level, highly detailed simulations of spinal networks have been developed. These models integrate multicompartment motoneuron representations, interneuronal connectivity, descending tracts, and electrical stimulation to simulate spinal processing and output [11]. While such models provide valuable insights into the feedforward effects of EES, they operate in an open-loop fashion, lacking integration with dynamic sensory feedback. As a result, they cannot fully capture the adaptive and time dependent nature of sensorimotor integration during movement.

Other studies have proposed closed-loop neuromuscular models by incorporating proprioceptive feedback, but they didn’t integrate EES stimulation. For instance, Sreenivasa et al. [45] developed a multi-level neuromuscular model of the human arm. Proprioceptive signals from muscle spindles were routed through monosynaptic excitatory and disynaptic inhibitory pathways to emulate spinal reflexes. More recent models have extended this approach by integrating descending commands and ascending sensory feedback [52, 23].

Efforts to combine spinal cord stimulation and sensorimotor feedback also include models that estimate afferent firing patterns during locomotion based on recorded joint kinematics and biomechanical simulations [16, 34]. However, these methods are limited by their reliance on offline computations and inverse kinematics, which restrict their ability to simulate dynamic sensorimotor interactions during ongoing movement. Moreover, these models are largely descriptive, as the effects of EES are incorporated as pre-recorded inputs rather than being generated within the model itself. Finally, their lack of generalization across varying biomechanical conditions hinders their translational application to diverse study cases.

The absence of such fully closed-loop models under EES limits our understanding of how EES interacts with the dynamic properties of the sensorimotor system, how these dynamics emerge from the interplay between EES and continuous sensory feedback. This highlights the need for an integrated, biologically plausible simulation framework that couples EES, spinal circuitry, musculoskeletal biomechanics, and real-time sensory feedback. Such a model would provide insights into the interaction between EES and spinal sensorimotor loop, and contribute to the development of adaptive, and more effective neuro-rehabilitation strategies.

1.4 Aim of the thesis

This thesis presents a biologically realistic simulation framework that integrates the Brian2 spiking neural simulator with OpenSim biomechanical modeling under EES stimulation. It enables real-time, bidirectional communication between neural and musculoskeletal systems, allowing dynamic feedback between muscle and spinal circuits in the context of EES stimulation.

While we designed a general and flexible pipeline, we chose to focus on the lower limb, specifically ankle kinematics. To demonstrate its application, we explore two case studies:

- **Ankle clonus**, a rhythmic, involuntary muscle contraction. Clonus typically arises from exaggerated proprioceptive feedback and is associated with upper motor neuron lesions. Although its exact mechanism remains debated [7], it is widely considered a hallmark of hyperreflexia and central nervous system dysfunction. Clinically, clonus is most commonly tested at the ankle joint by rapidly dorsiflexing the foot, which in affected individuals triggers a series of involuntary rhythmic ankle contractions [53] Figure 1.1. While clonus can be observed in any muscles [7], we focused on the Soleus muscle, which is frequently studied in clonus related literature due to its relatively high density of muscle spindles compared to other lower limb muscles, such as the gastrocnemius or tibialis anterior [2]. Moreover, to model ankle clonus, we consider a monosynaptic reflex circuit and we apply a torque at the ankle joint.
- **EES-evoked multi-muscle motor activity**, which involve coordinated activation patterns across multiple muscles. The understanding of these patterns are critical for restoring functional locomotion after spinal cord injury. Figure 1.2 illustrates the stimulation setup. We choose as muscles flexor, the tibialis anterior and as muscle extensor, the medial gastrocnemius and we apply EES on the segments L4, S1, S2. We consider a reciprocal inhibitory neural network for the spinal circuit.

Figure 1.1: **Case study 1: Ankle Clonus.** In response to dorsiflexion of the ankle joint, a series of involuntary rhythmic oscillations is observed. We investigate the underlying mechanisms that could explain this phenomenon, which is especially common in patients with spinal cord injury [35].

Figure 1.2: **Case study 2: EES-evoked multi-muscle motor activity.** Epidural electrical stimulation is applied at the L4–S2 spinal segments. We focus on the tibialis anterior and medial gastrocnemius muscles, given their critical role in locomotion.

Chapter 2

Methods

Here we describe the architecture, parameter choices, and assumptions underlying the closed-loop model. This chapter is structured as follows: first, we detail each component of the closed-loop model individually. We then present the integration of the stimulus (EES for the case study 2 and mechanical perturbations at the ankle joint for case study 1). Finally, we explain how these components are combined to form a fully integrated closed-loop framework.

2.1 Overall computational model

In this thesis, we develop a closed-loop neuromusculoskeletal model that integrates the following components:

- a proprioceptive feedback model incorporating multiple sensory modalities (group Ia, II, and Ib fibers);
- a model of the interaction between EES and afferent fiber;
- a spiking neural network of spinal circuits implemented in Brian2;
- a model translating motoneuron spiking activity into muscle activation dynamics;
- a biomechanical model of the human lower limbs using OpenSim.

Figure 2.1: **Overview of the closed-loop architecture.** The simulation pipeline integrates a biologically realistic spinal circuit, a motoneuron-to-muscle activation model, a musculoskeletal model, and proprioceptive feedback. Two types of stimulation are supported: mechanical perturbations applied at the ankle joint and EES targeting the dorsal root of the spinal cord.

2.1.1 Muscle spindle and Golgi tendon organ models

Role of Ia, II, Ib afferents

To reproduce accurate human movement, we model three types of proprioceptive afferent fibers: Ia, II, and Ib.

Mechanical quantities such as muscle stretch, stretch velocity, and tendon tension throughout the musculotendon complex are sensed by proprioceptive sensory organs, which interact with the neural system. The Ia and II pathways primarily convey stretch-related information from muscle spindles. The Ia fibers are sensitive to both dynamic stretch and stretch velocity, while II fibers predominantly encode static muscle length. A key novelty of our model, compared to the work of Moraud et al. [34], is the inclusion of Golgi tendon organ (GTO) feedback via the Ib pathway. This feedback encodes muscle force and contributes to protective inhibition during excessive force generation. The addition of the Ib pathway provides more realistic proprioceptive feedback and enables modulation of biomechanical responses in our model.

Afferent firing rate equations

To ensure physiological relevance, we adapted and scaled afferent firing rate models proposed by Prochazka et al., Crago et al., and Haggie et al., [40, 39, 12, 19] which were originally derived from cat experiments or earlier models, adjusting them to better reflect the lower firing rates typically observed in humans. In general, human muscle afferents rarely exceed 50 Hz [50], and under low-movement conditions, their rates often remain below 30 Hz [16].

The scaling factors applied to each model are as follows:

- **Ia fibers:** Adapted from Prochazka et al [40] and Haggie et al. [19], the baseline mean Ia firing rate term in the equation was scaled by dividing the baseline rate by a factor of 4.
- **II fibers:** Adapted from Prochazka et al. [39], the baseline mean II firing rate was scaled by a factor of 5.
- **Ib fibers:** Adapted from Crago et al. [12], and Haggie et al [19], the Ib firing rate was scaled by a factor of 2.

The resulting firing rate equations used in our model are:

$$Ia = 10 + 2 \cdot \text{stretch} + 4.3 \cdot \text{sign}(\text{stretch}) \cdot |\text{stretch}|^{0.6} \quad (2.1)$$

$$II = 20 + 13.5 \cdot \text{stretch} \quad (2.2)$$

$$Ib = 28.5 \cdot \left(\frac{\text{force}}{\text{force}_{\max}} \right)^{0.2} \quad (2.3)$$

where:

- stretch: Normalized muscle fiber stretch.

- stretch: Muscle fiber stretch velocity.
- force: Muscle force.
- force_{max}: Maximum isometric force (used for normalization).

Muscle stretch is computed as:

$$\text{stretch} = \frac{L_{\text{fiber}}}{L_{\text{fiber, rest}}} - 1,$$

where L_{fiber} is the current fiber length and $L_{\text{fiber, rest}}$ is the rest length.

2.1.2 Spiking neural network

Neuron models

Afferent fibers are modeled as inhomogeneous Poisson processes. To simulate their spiking activity, we use the Bernoulli approximation. In each small time intervals Δt , a spike occurs with probability:

$$P(\text{spike in } [t, t + \Delta t]) = \lambda(t) \cdot \Delta t,$$

where $\lambda(t)$, is the mean firing rate of the afferents calculated previously. This approximation relies on the following assumptions:

- The time step Δt is sufficiently small such that $\lambda(t) \cdot \Delta t \ll 1$, ensuring that the probability of more than one spike in a time bin is negligible.
- Spikes event are independent across time bins.
- The firing rate $\lambda(t)$ varies slowly relative to Δt , allowing it to be considered constant within each bin.

Interneuron and motoneurons are modeled as leaky integrate-and-fire (LIF) units, to balance biological plausibility with computational simplicity. The membrane potential $v(t)$ of each neuron evolves according to the following differential equation:

$$\frac{dv}{dt} = \frac{g_L(E_{\text{leak}} - v) + I_{\text{syn}}}{C_m}, \tag{2.4}$$

where:

- $v(t)$ is the membrane potential at time t ,
- g_L is the leak conductance,
- E_{leak} is the leak (resting) potential,
- I_{syn} is the total synaptic input current,

- C_m is the membrane capacitance.

This equation models the passive integration of input currents and the intrinsic leakage of charge across the membrane. When the membrane potential reaches a threshold value v_{th} , the neuron emits a spike. Immediately after spiking, the membrane potential is reset to a specified reset value v_{reset} , and the neuron enters a refractory period during which it cannot fire again.

Table 2.1: Biophysical parameters used in the spiking neuron model.

Parameter	Description	Value
T_{refr}	Refractory period	2 ms
E_{leaky}	Leak reversal potential	-70 mV
g_L	Leak conductance	10 nS
C_m	Membrane capacitance	0.3 nF
E_{ex}	Excitatory reversal potential	0 mV
τ_e	Excitatory synaptic time constant	0.5 ms
E_{inh}	Inhibitory reversal potential	-75 mV
τ_i	Inhibitory synaptic time constant	2.5 ms
V_{thresh}	Spike threshold voltage	-50 mV

Neural population

To ensure biologically realistic neuron densities, we base our model parameters on published estimates of human muscle spindle [2] and motor unit counts [15, 13, 29].

Muscle	Spindle Count	Motor Unit Count
tibialis anterior	284	200–445
gastrocnemius (medial)	156	579
soleus	408	>500

Table 2.2: Estimated spindle and motor unit counts for key lower limb muscles, based on data from Banks [2], Feinstein et al. [15], and other sources [13, 29].

Synapses

Synapse connection

Neuronal populations were connected probabilistically with fixed random seed for reproducibility. Each connection assigned a synaptic weight reflecting its strength.

Excitatory synapse

Excitatory synaptic conductances are modeled as exponentially decaying variables with time constant τ_e . The dynamics are described by the differential equation:

$$\frac{dg_e}{dt} = -\frac{g_e}{\tau_e}, \quad (2.5)$$

where g_e represents the excitatory conductance. Upon the arrival of a presynaptic spike at synapse i , the conductance is instantaneously incremented by the synaptic weight w_i :

$$g_e \leftarrow g_e + w_i.$$

The resulting excitatory synaptic current contribution is given by:

$$I_{\text{syn,e}} = g_e(E_e - v),$$

where E_e is the excitatory reversal potential and v is the membrane potential.

Inhibitory synapse

Inhibitory synaptic conductances are modeled using an α -function :

$$\text{PSP}(t) = \frac{t}{\tau} e^{-t/\tau}, \quad (2.6)$$

where τ is the time constant governing the time course of the postsynaptic potential (PSP). For compatibility with brian2 simulation frameworks, this can be equivalently expressed in differential form using an auxiliary variable x :

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dg_i}{dt} = \frac{x - g_i}{\tau_i}, \\ \frac{dx}{dt} = -\frac{x}{\tau_i}, \end{cases} \quad (2.7)$$

where g_i is the inhibitory conductance and τ_i is the inhibitory time constant. Upon arrival of a presynaptic spike at synapse i , the variable x is incremented by the synaptic weight w_i :

$$x \leftarrow x + w_i.$$

The inhibitory synaptic current contribution is then computed as:

$$I_{\text{syn,i}} = g_i(E_i - v),$$

where E_i is the inhibitory reversal potential.

This approach provides a biophysically realistic representation of synaptic dynamics, faithfully reproducing the temporal profiles of excitatory and inhibitory postsynaptic currents observed experimentally.

Variability in synapse transmission

To reflect the biological variability observed in synaptic transmission, we introduced noise into the initial synaptic weights. The noisy synaptic weight w_i is defined as:

$$w_i \sim \mathcal{N}(w_0, (0.2 \cdot w_0)^2)$$

where w_0 is the baseline synaptic weight and the coefficient 0.2 reflects the level of variability (20%) around this baseline. This Gaussian distribution models natural heterogeneity in synapse structure. The weights are constrained to remain non-negative, ensuring physiological realism. Similarly, synaptic delays were jittered with a Gaussian distribution around a mean of 1 ms to introduce temporal variability in spike transmission.

Case studies

Clonus modeling: monosynaptic circuit

To investigate the mechanisms underlying clonus, we implemented a minimal spinal circuit: motoneurons innervating a single muscle (soleus) with monosynaptic Ia afferent input. This simplified reflex loop isolates stretch feedback and reveals how it alone can generate the oscillatory activity characteristic of clonus.

The model includes a population of 400 Ia afferent neurons and 500 motoneurons. Ia afferents connect to motoneurons with a probability of 0.6, and each synapse is assigned a weight of 2.1 nS.

Motor pattern formation during EES: reciprocal inhibitory spinal circuit

To simulate motor like rhythmic activity elicited by EES, we constructed a reciprocal inhibitory neural circuit. This network includes:

- Ia, II, and Ib afferents
- Interneuron populations composed of excitatory and inhibitory neurons for Ib pathway and reciprocal inhibitory interneurons mediating mutual inhibition between antagonistic muscle groups.
- Motoneuron pools for both flexor and extensor muscles.

Figure 2.2 illustrates the architecture of our spinal circuit model. Ia afferents provide direct excitatory input to agonist motoneurons, while group II afferents modulate tonic activity via excitatory interneurons. Reciprocal inhibition is mediated by inhibitory interneurons activated by both Ia and II inputs, suppressing antagonist motoneurons activity. Additionally, inhibitory interneurons receiving input from Ib and Ia afferents prevent overexcitation of the agonist muscle. We adopt the same Ia and II afferent pathway network as described by Moraud et al. [34]. Ib pathway is adapted from neuronal network developed by Stienen et al.[46] and Bashor et al.[3].

Synaptic weights and connectivity probabilities were adapted from validated values reported by Moraud et al. [34] to generate realistic motoneuron firing patterns across both muscle groups. For type Ib afferent pathways, synaptic weights were estimated and manually

Figure 2.2: **Reciprocal inhibitory spinal circuit.** The network integrates excitatory input from Ia afferents to motoneurons (MN), tonic drive via group II pathways and excitatory interneuron (exc), and inhibitory control through inhibitory interneurons from Ib pathway (inhb) and reciprocal inhibitory interneuron (inh) targeting both agonist and antagonist motoneurons.

tuned to achieve physiologically plausible network dynamics. A summary of the connection parameters, including synaptic weights and probabilities, is provided in Table 2.3.

Due to limited quantitative data on spinal interneuron populations in humans, we adopted a simplified symmetric model. The flexor (e.g., tibialis anterior) and extensor (e.g., gastrocnemius) networks contain equivalent numbers of neurons. The table below summarizes the neuron populations used in the bimuscle spinal model 2.4.

Table 2.3: Synaptic parameters of the reciprocal inhibitory network: weights and connection probabilities

Pre-synaptic neuron	Post-synaptic neuron	Weight (nS)	Connection Probability
Ia_flexor	MN_flexor	2.10	0.70
Ia_extensor	MN_extensor	2.10	0.70
Ia_flexor	inh_flexor	3.64	0.70
Ia_extensor	inh_extensor	3.64	0.70
Ia_flexor	inhb_flexor	0.50	0.60
Ia_extensor	inhb_extensor	0.50	0.60
II_flexor	exc_flexor	1.65	0.80
II_extensor	exc_extensor	1.65	0.80
II_flexor	inh_flexor	2.19	0.70
II_extensor	inh_extensor	2.19	0.70
Ib_flexor	inhb_flexor	1.65	0.60
Ib_extensor	inhb_extensor	1.65	0.60
exc_flexor	MN_flexor	0.70	0.50
exc_extensor	MN_extensor	0.70	0.50
inhb_flexor	MN_flexor	0.20	0.60
inhb_extensor	MN_extensor	0.20	0.60
inh_flexor	MN_extensor	0.20	0.60
inh_extensor	MN_flexor	0.20	0.60
inh_flexor	inh_extensor	0.76	0.30
inh_extensor	inh_flexor	0.76	0.30

Note: Weights are given in nanosiemens (nS). Connection probabilities are unitless values between 0 and 1.

2.1.3 Muscle activation model

We implemented the muscle activation model proposed by Caillet et al. [8] to simulate the transformation of motoneuron spike trains into continuous muscle activation signals. This model is based on experimental data and captures each biological stage of neuromuscular transmission, from motoneuron firing to muscle activation. It also distinguishes between fast and slow motor unit (MU) types.

Activation dynamics are computed individually for each MU. The overall muscle activation is then obtained by averaging the activations across all motor units.

Table 2.4: Neuron populations for gastrocnemius/tibialis reciprocal inhibitory neuronal network

Neuron Type	Count
Ia (flexor / extensor)	200 / 200
II (flexor / extensor)	200 / 200
Excitatory interneurons (flexor / extensor)	400 / 400
Inhibitory interneurons (flexor / extensor)	400 / 400
Motoneurons (flexor / extensor)	300 / 300

While the model provides an accurate representation of muscle behavior, its use of non-linear differential equations increases computational complexity. To mitigate this, activation dynamics for each motor unit are computed in parallel. Finally, the system of equation is solved using the Runge-Kutta 45 method with adaptive step sizing for numerical stability and computational efficiency.

Mathematical formulation

Action potential generation

The spiking times of each motoneuron are transformed into smoothed waveforms to enhance numerical stability:

$$e(t) = \begin{cases} V_e \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{T}(t - t_i)\right), & \text{for } t_i \leq t \leq t_i + \frac{T}{2} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Here, t_i denotes the spike time, T is the duration of the action potential, and V_e is its peak voltage amplitude.

Fiber action potential dynamics

The fiber action potential train $u(t)$ is modeled as a second-order response to the motoneuron input $e(t)$:

$$\frac{d^2u}{dt^2} = a_1e(t) - a_2u - a_3\frac{du}{dt}$$

Parameter a_1 controls the peak to peak amplitude of the fiber action potential, while a_2 and a_3 govern the time-to-peak and exponential decay, respectively.

Calcium dynamics

The calcium concentration $c(t)$ in the muscle fiber sarcoplasm is driven by the fiber action potential $u(t)$, and follows:

$$\frac{d^2c}{dt^2} = b_1u - \frac{1}{f_{1l}} \left(b_2f_{2l}c + b_3\frac{dc}{dt} \right)$$

Here, b_1 determines the amplitude of the calcium twitch, while b_2 and b_3 define the time-to-peak and decay characteristics. The scaling factors f_{1l} and f_{2l} parameter depend to the MU fiber length. In the simulations, we fix the normalized MU fiber length at 1.0.

Calcium-Troponin binding

The formation of Ca-Tn complexes, resulting from calcium binding to troponin in the sarcomere, is modeled as:

$$\frac{dP}{dt} = \frac{c_1}{f_{3l}} \left(\frac{P_0}{f_{4l}} - P \right) c^2 - \frac{c_2}{f_{5l}} P$$

Here, P represents the Ca-Tn concentration, and P_0 the maximum binding capacity. The parameters c_1 and c_2 are respectively the forward and backward reaction rates of the Ca-Tn binding-unbinding process. The scaling factors f_{3l} , f_{4l} , and f_{5l} depend of the MU fiber length

Motor unit activation

Finally, the activation state $a(t)$ of each motor unit is derived from the Ca-Tn concentration:

$$\frac{da}{dt} = d_1 P - \frac{a}{d_2 + d_3 P}$$

Parameters d_1 , d_2 , and d_3 respectively control the twitch amplitude, time-to-peak, and half-relaxation time of MU activation.

Model parameters and twitch type choice

The model parameters for both slow and fast twitch muscle types are detailed in Table 2.5. Regarding the choice muscle twitch types, for case study 1, centered on ankle clonus, we used slow-twitch dynamics. For case study 2, which focuses on multi-muscle motor patterns under EES, we adopted fast-twitch muscle dynamics. This choice is supported by the findings of Gollnick et al. [17], who reported that the soleus muscle predominantly consists of slow-twitch (Type I) fibers, with an average 80% across subjects (range: 64–100% in the study). In contrast, the gastrocnemius and vastus lateralis muscles contain approximately 57% slow-twitch fibers on average (range: 34–82% in the study).

Table 2.5: **Model parameters for slow and fast muscle fibers.** In case study 1 (ankle clonus), we modeled the activation dynamics of the soleus using slow-twitch fiber parameters. In Case Study 2 (multi-muscle activation under EES), the gastrocnemius and tibialis anterior were modeled using fast-twitch fiber dynamics to better reflect their physiological properties.

Parameter	Slow Fiber	Fast Fiber
<i>AP Generation</i>		
V_e	90	90
t_{ap}	0.0014	0.0014
<i>Fiber AP Dynamics</i>		
a_1	7×10^7	7×10^7
a_2	5×10^7	5×10^7
a_3	2×10^4	2×10^4
<i>Calcium Dynamics</i>		
b_1	0.4	0.9
b_2	1.5×10^5	4.3×10^5
b_3	2.5×10^3	2.4×10^3
<i>Calcium-Troponin Binding</i>		
c_1	6×10^{12}	1×10^{12}
c_2	21	41
P_0	1.7×10^{-4}	3.8×10^{-4}
<i>Motor Unit Activation</i>		
d_1	1×10^5	1×10^5
d_2	0.024	0.024
d_3	270	270

2.1.4 Musculoskeletal model: OpenSim Gait2392

We utilized the OpenSim `gait2392_millard2012` model [36] to perform forward dynamics simulations. Using OpenSim’s forward dynamics framework, we simulated the skeletal and muscular movements resulting from given muscle activations over time. Specifically, we calculated muscle stretches and forces to estimate afferent firing rates. Additionally, we computed the resulting ankle joint kinematics.

Model specifications

The `gait2392_millard2012` is a 23-DOF musculoskeletal model with 92 musculotendon actuators representing 76 distinct muscles across the lower limbs and torso. The 23 DOFs include hip, knee, and ankle joint movements (flexion/extension, abduction/adduction, internal/external rotation, dorsiflexion/plantarflexion, inversion/eversion), as well as spinal motion. The pelvis degrees of freedom were constrained, since ground reaction forces were not included in the model.

Muscle dynamics modeling

Muscle dynamics are modeled using the Millard et al. [31] damped equilibrium Hill-type model with elastic tendons, incorporating active and passive force-length relationships, force-velocity dynamics, and tendon compliance for physiologically realistic muscle behavior.

Model validation and implementation

This model is widely adopted and validated against experimental gait data, offering both biomechanical accuracy and reproducibility. Its C++ implementation ensures computational efficiency for real-time simulations.

2.2 Stimulations

2.2.1 Case study 1: mechanical stimulus

To induce clonus, we applied an ankle perturbation with an initial Gaussian torque burst followed by a sustained constant torque, mimicking the clinical patellar tendon tap.

Based on Pei et al. [37], effective clonus requires rapid dorsiflexion ($> 200^\circ/\text{s}$) and sustained torque ($> 3 \text{ Nm}$). Our torque profile meets these criteria, producing an initial acceleration and constant load to sustain oscillations (Fig. 2.3).

The torque $\tau(t)$ is defined as:

$$\tau(t) = \begin{cases} A \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{(t - t_{\text{peak}})^2}{2\sigma^2}\right), & \text{if } \tau(t) > \tau_{\text{sustain}} \\ \tau_{\text{sustain}}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2.8)$$

where:

- $A = 20 \text{ Nm}$ is the peak amplitude of the torque,

- $t_{\text{peak}} = 100 \text{ ms}$ is the time at which the Gaussian burst peaks,
- $\sigma = 50 \text{ ms}$ is the standard deviation controlling the width of the Gaussian,
- $\tau_{\text{sustain}} = 5 \text{ Nm}$ is the level of sustained torque applied after the burst.

Figure 2.3: **Torque profile applied to the ankle joint to elicit clonus.** The curve consists of an initial Gaussian burst followed by a sustained constant torque, designed to replicate the stimulation conditions shown by Pei et al. [37].

2.2.2 Case study 2: EES stimulation

We simulate the delivery of EES using cathodal square pulses with a fixed duration of $500 \mu\text{s}$. The model explicitly incorporates key stimulation parameters, including stimulation intensity, stimulation frequency, and the spatial location of the stimulation site.

Key assumptions and hypotheses

In this study, we assume that the frequency of EES modulates the firing rate of recruited afferent fibers but does not alter which and how many fibers are recruited. We further hypothesize that the amplitude of stimulation determines the proportion and type of fibers recruited, without affecting their firing rate. Moreover, we hypothesize that direct motoneuron activation occurs only at high stimulation intensities [18] and is negligible at the amplitudes considered here, thereby preserving proprioceptive information.

Note: Although our simulation pipeline can model direct motoneuron recruitment, this feature is intentionally disabled in the present study to isolate afferent-mediated effects.

Stimulation amplitude, site and fiber recruitment

To explicitly model the relationship between the fraction of recruited fibers as a function of stimulation current, we used recruitment curves derived from the work of Capogrosso et al. [10].

Capogrosso et al. [10] explicitly modeled recruitment curves across different spinal segments. However, most of these segment-specific results were not preserved, and we were only able to recover them for the S1 spinal segment. To approximate the recruitment curve for other spinal segments, we extrapolated them from the S1 recruitment curve. This extrapolation was guided by anatomical considerations, specifically, the organization of spinal roots, spatial motor mapping and by experimental data on segmental muscle responses. For this purpose, we relied on segmental innervation patterns reported by Hofstoetter et al. [22] and relative muscle activation data from Schirmer et al. [43].

Metric	Muscle	L4	L5	S1	S2
Segmental Innervation (%) [22]	TA	96%	73%	30%	4%
	GA	11%	44%	96%	80%
Relative Response (%) [43]	TA	35.6%	44.5%	19.5%	0%
	GA	11.2%	23.9%	53.7%	50%

Table 2.6: **Segmental Innervation and EES-Evoked Muscle Responses Across Spinal Roots.** Summary of the segmental innervation percentages (from Hofstoetter et al. [22]) and relative response percentages during EES (from Schirmer et al. [43]) for Tibialis Anterior (TA) and Gastrocnemius (GA) across spinal roots.

Stimulation frequency and afferent modulation

The frequency of EES modulates the firing rates of the recruited afferent fibers. This interaction is both non-linear and phase-dependent: if a stimulation pulse occurs during the depolarization or refractory period of an afferent, it may fail to evoke an action potential [34].

To simulate the effect of EES on afferent firing rates, we modify the previously defined firing rate $\lambda(t)$ in the Bernoulli approximation of the inhomogeneous Poisson process. Specifically, we incorporate the EES frequency as an additive term for afferent fibers recruited by stimulation. The firing rate is thus given by:

$$\lambda(t) = f_{\text{baseline}}(t) + f_{\text{EES}},$$

where $f_{\text{baseline}}(t)$ represents the intrinsic (i.e., pre-EES) firing rate of the afferent, computed from the muscle spindle model, and f_{EES} denotes the frequency of the applied EES stimulus.

To prevent physiologically implausible high-frequency spiking, we enforce a refractory period of 2 ms following each spike.

Note: This simplified additive model likely overestimates the true afferent firing rate under EES, as discussed in the Appendix.

(a) Recruitment curve at site S1

(b) Recruitment curve at site L4

(c) Recruitment curve at site S2

Figure 2.4: **Recruitment curves for stimulation at L4, S1, and S2.** The S1 curve is based on the model by Capogrosso et al. [10], while L4 and S2 are extrapolated from spinal anatomy and experimental muscle responses.

For afferent fibers not recruited by EES, the firing rate remains governed solely by the baseline physiological activity:

$$\lambda(t) = f_{\text{baseline}}(t).$$

Figure 2.5: **EES-afferents coupling method:** Afferent firing following EES is modeled as a combination of natural firing and EES-induced spikes for stimulated fibers. Non stimulated fibers exhibit only natural firing. This combination should accounts for collisions between EES-induced and naturally occurring spikes, as well as the neuron’s refractory period during which new inputs cannot be integrated. In practice, this is implemented using a Poisson process with a rate equal to the sum of the natural afferent firing rate and the EES frequency, and a refractory period of 2 ms. *Source:* [34]

2.3 Closed-loop timing

We now describe how the previously introduced models temporally interact within the overall framework (closed-loop model) to replicate natural neuromuscular feedback dynamics.

2.3.1 Reaction time

To capture the temporal dynamics of sensorimotor interactions, the closed-loop model operates in discrete cycle defined by a key parameter: the **reaction time** T_{reaction} . This parameter encapsulates the full loop delay involved in processing and responding to sensory input, including:

- the time required for sensory receptors (e.g., muscle spindles and Golgi tendon organs) to detect changes in muscle length, tension, or force;
- the conduction delay as sensory signals travel via afferent fibers to the spinal cord;
- the synaptic and processing time within spinal interneurons and motoneurons;
- the conduction delay of efferent signals traveling back to the muscle;
- the time it takes for the muscle fibers to generate force in response to motoneuron activation;

2.3.2 Sub-models interactions

Each simulation cycle of duration T_{reaction} consists of three stages:

1. compute the current muscle state (e.g., length, force, velocity), starting from rest or the output of the previous cycle;
2. simulate the neural dynamics in response to sensory inputs derived from the muscle state;
3. use the resulting motoneuron output to compute new muscle activation and update the biomechanical state;

The updated muscle dynamics then becomes the basis for computing new sensory feedback in the next cycle, thereby closing the sensorimotor loop. This ensures that the system reacts to itself, after T_{reaction} in accordance with the physiological latency. By aligning the duration of each simulation cycle with the natural physiological reaction time, the model ensures biological plausibility and enables real-time feedback behavior.

2.3.3 Delayed II pathway

Another challenge is longer latency of the II pathway, due to the difference in conduction velocity between Ia (80–100 m/s) and II afferent pathways (30–40 m/s)[19]. We assume that the measured reaction time primarily reflects the faster Ia fibers, and not the slower II fibers.

Assuming an anatomical distance of 1 m between the ankle and spinal cord, the estimated delay difference is:

$$\Delta t_{\text{Ia, II}} = \frac{1}{50} = 0.02 \text{ s} = 20 \text{ ms}$$

In simulation, we use a buffer of muscle stretch values and apply a time-shifted (delayed) stretch signal when computing the II afferent firing rate.

2.3.4 Incorporating reflex latencies

To simulate physiologically realistic feedback dynamics, we incorporated known latency values for spinal reflexes. Based on the work of Hiraok [21], the soleus reflex latency is approximately 40 ms, while the gastrocnemius reflex latency is 80 ms. Additionally, tibialis anterior, exhibits a longer latency of about 120 ms, as reported by Mauritz et al [28]. In the bimuscle model (case study 2), we set the reaction time to an intermediate value of 100 ms.

2.4 Additional analysis

2.4.1 Sensitivity analysis

This bimuscle model (case study 2) contains many more parameters compared to the clonus model, and consequently, we performed a sensitivity analysis to assess the influence of individual parameters and to decouple their roles. To do so, we varied each model parameter independently by multiplying their baseline values by multiplying their baseline values by the following factors: $\frac{1}{2}$, $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$, $\frac{10}{11}$, $\frac{11}{10}$, $\sqrt{2}$, and 2.

For parameters such as the probability of connection or resting membrane potential, for which doubling would not be biologically meaningful, we manually selected values centered around the baseline. As a summary metric describing ankle movement, we computed the root mean square (RMS) of ankle velocity, which effectively quantifies the overall movement intensity and variability over time, making it sensitive to changes in system dynamics while being robust to transient fluctuations. Sensitivity was computed as the ratio of the relative change in output to the relative change in the parameter:

$$\Delta_{\text{RMS}} = \frac{|\text{RMS joint velocity} - \text{baseline metric}|}{|\text{baseline metric}|}$$
$$\Delta_{\text{param}} = \frac{|\text{param value} - \text{original param}|}{|\text{original param}|}$$
$$\text{sensitivity} = \frac{\Delta_{\text{RMS}}}{\Delta_{\text{param}}}$$

We then identified the ten most influential parameters.

2.4.2 Optimizer

Inspired by the work of Moraud et al., we developed a model-based optimization framework to tune the EES frequency such that the resulting motor activation patterns is closer to the natural muscle activity during walking.

To define our target activation patterns, we leveraged the Muscles in Time (MinT) dataset [25, 26, 24], specifically the KIT subset, which contains synthetic muscle activation calculated using biomechanical simulations in OpenSim from motion capture sequences.

The walking sequences of the right gastrocnemius and tibialis anterior muscles activation was segmented using vertical ground reaction force data to detect foot contact events, and each sequence was time normalized to span 0% to 100% of the gait cycle. By averaging 82 gait cycles, we derived a smooth, representative “natural” activation profile. We identified the flexor and extensor phases based on the intersection points of their respective activation curves, with slight adjustments to anticipate transitions.

Our stimulation strategy alternated between the L4 and S2 spinal segments to target tibialis anterior and medial gastrocnemius afferents, respectively. Accordingly, we implemented two separate optimizers: one for tuning the EES frequency at L4 during the flexor phase (stance), and another for tuning the frequency at S2 during the extensor phase (swing). We compared the optimized results against a baseline condition where a fixed frequency of 40 Hz was applied equally at both L4 and S2 during their respective phase. Stimulation amplitude was fixed at 300 μ A.

For both optimizers, we employed the bounded Brent algorithm from SciPy, which combines Golden section search and parabolic interpolation within a specified frequency range (0–100 Hz). The objective function minimized the root mean square error (RMSE) between the model-predicted muscle activations and the "natural" activation profiles derived from the MinT dataset.

Chapter 3

Results

3.1 Case study 1: ankle clonus modeling

To evaluate the validity of our model, we simulated a clinical scenario of ankle clonus. As a baseline, we first modeled the healthy condition, which typically exhibits only one or two oscillations before the system returns to a stable state [53]. Pathological clonus was then elicited by increasing the excitability of the spinal circuit. This was achieved by lowering the motoneuron firing threshold from -50 mV to -55 mV, mimicking the effect of reduced supraspinal inhibition. Under this condition, the system exhibited sustained rhythmic oscillations with a frequency of approximately 5 Hz and an angular amplitude of about 5° . Raster plot show that a key characteristic of clonus is synchronous motor spiking Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: **From healthy to ankle clonus.** Pathological rhythmic muscle contractions at 5–6 Hz emerge in our model when the motoneuron firing threshold is decreased, simulating increased excitability of the motoneuron pool. This condition mimics the effects of diminished supraspinal drive, which reduce spinal inhibition and promote abnormal synchronous oscillatory activity of the motoneurons.

3.2 Case study 2: multi-muscles motor rhythms under EES

3.2.1 Sensitivity analysis

First, we fixed the EES stimulation site at S1, while keeping the frequency of stimulation at 50 Hz and the current at 300 μ A. Then, we analyzed the influence of key parameters, including biophysical properties, neuron population sizes, and synaptic connectivity on the root mean square of the ankle velocity. The global sensitivity analysis confirmed that, as expected, parameters governing the excitability of the neuronal circuit were among the most influential. In particular, fundamental biophysical properties such as the resting membrane potential and the spiking threshold had a substantial impact on motor output. Additionally, the initial synaptic connections between afferents and interneurons emerged as critical factors. Finally, we observed that variations in population sizes had a relatively limited effect on the system's dynamics, Figure 3.2.

To further explore the system's behavior, we analyzed its dynamics across a wide range of parameter combinations, searching for bifurcations. Three main dynamical regimes emerged from this analysis. The first was a stable oscillatory pattern. Interestingly, the oscillation period remained largely stable across most parameter variations. Only a few parameters, namely the reaction time, excitatory synaptic time constant, inhibitory synaptic time constant, and the spindle equation themselves, significantly affected the period. Specifically, the oscillation period increased with a longer reaction time, a longer synaptic inhibitory time constant, or a shorter synaptic excitatory time constant, see Figures 3.3 and 3.4. The second regime observed is the preferential activation of one muscle over the other. This was typically observed when mutual inhibition was strong due to higher inhibitory weights, connection probabilities, or longer inhibitory time constants or when network excitability was increased. The third one is agonist and antagonist co-activations. This was observed when the self-inhibition in the reciprocal inhibitory network is too weak, see Figure 3.3.

Finally, proprioceptive feedback plays an essential role in generating flexor and extensor alternating rhythms. Introducing a baseline firing rate that is independent of the muscle state abolishes the flexor/extensor oscillations and leads to the preferential activation of a single muscle, as illustrated in Figure 3.5.

Figure 3.2: Top 10 most influential parameters on the ankle velocity RMS

Motoneuron spikes

Figure 3.3: **Impact of inhibitory synaptic time constant on motoneuron dynamics.** Varying the inhibitory synaptic time constant (τ_i) produces three distinct regimes: coactivation, alternation, and dominant activation. Interestingly, increasing (τ_i) from 2.2 ms and 2.9 ms, increase the period of oscillation from 2.5 Hz to 2 Hz.

(a) Smooth motoneuron firing rate (kernel density estimation method) for reaction time of 100 ms (baseline)

(b) Smooth motoneuron firing rate (kernel density estimation method) for a reaction time of 300 ms

Figure 3.4: **Effect of reaction time on motoneuron firing periodicity.** Short reaction times (e.g., 100 ms) produce faster oscillatory patterns with periods around 500 ms, whereas longer reaction times (e.g., 300 ms) slow the alternation, resulting in firing periods close to 1 s.

(a) Motoneuron spike trains with sensory feedback

(b) Motoneuron spike trains without sensory feedback

Figure 3.5: **Effect of sensory feedback on motoneuron spiking.**

Rhythmic flexor-extensor patterns rely on sensory feedback for coordination. Without sensory feedback (i.e., with constant afferent input), the network exhibits dominant activation.

3.2.2 Overview of the influence of the stimulation site

Then, to investigate how different spinal stimulation sites shape motor output, we compared the effects of EES applied at spinal segments L4, S1, and S2 with a EES frequency of 50 Hz, and a current of 300 μ A. These segments project to distinct root, L4 predominantly innervate the tibialis anterior and S2, the medial gastrocnemius, while S1 provides a more balanced recruitment of both.

Our simulations reveal that imbalanced recruitment of flexor and extensor afferents results in sustained activation of a single muscle group, Figure 3.6.

In contrast, stimulation at S1, which produces balanced recruitment of flexor and extensor afferents, elicits stable flexor-extensor alternating motor rhythms at physiological frequencies (2 Hz), closely resembling natural locomotor dynamics (Figure 3.6).

In SCI patients, the descending control of spinal interneurons, especially those involved in reciprocal inhibition, is often impaired, leading to reduced reciprocal inhibition [51]. To model this effect, we decreased the synaptic weight from Ia/II afferents to reciprocal inhibitory interneurons by a factor of 5. As a result, we observed increased co-activation of antagonist muscles at all stimulation sites, with the most pronounced effect at the S1 segment, Figure 3.7. As expected, unbalanced afferent recruitment (site L4, S2) for the tibialis and the gastrocnemius reduce muscle co-activation.

Figure 3.6: **Motoneuron activity, muscle activation, and ankle kinematics across different stimulation sites.** Imbalanced recruitment of flexor and extensor afferents (e.g., during stimulation at L4 or S2) modifies the relative dominance of flexor versus extensor afferent firing rates (pre-EES vs. post-EES) across movement phases, leading to selective muscle activation (frequency: 50 Hz, intensity: 300 μ A).

Figure 3.7: **Motoneuron activity and muscle activation across stimulation sites with reduced reciprocal inhibition (SCI).**

Reduced reciprocal inhibition results in increased co-activation of flexor and extensor muscles (frequency: 50 Hz, intensity: 300 μ A)

3.2.3 Effect of EES frequency and current on evoked muscle responses

We then leveraged the computational model to investigate the impact of EES frequency and current on evoked muscle responses.

First, we focus on the site S2, and we examined the effects of EES frequency and amplitude on motoneuron firing rates, muscle activation, and resulting ankle kinematics. We found that increasing the frequency from 10 to 70 Hz resulted in a linear increase in motoneuron firing rate, muscle activation, and ankle angle amplitude. A similar trend was observed when increasing the EES amplitude from 200 μ A to 450 μ A, which corresponds to a variation between 1 and 2.5 times the motoneuron activation threshold. However, we observed that high-frequency stimulation produced qualitatively different motor outputs compared to high-amplitude stimulation. Specifically, high frequencies led to tetanic and sustained muscle contractions, whereas high amplitudes caused a rapid saturation of the response due to the recruitment of all available fibers as illustrated in Figures 3.8.

Secondly, at the site S1, we observed that varying the frequency and stimulation amplitude does not affect the oscillation period or the relative activation between agonist and antagonist muscles. However, low stimulation settings (e.g., 20 Hz or amplitudes corresponding to the motoneuron threshold) prevent the generation of rhythmic oscillatory patterns (this likely results from contractions that are too weak to produce sufficient sensory feedback necessary to generate rhythmic activity). Furthermore, we observed at every frequencies, a progressive increase oscillation amplitude for the flexor and extensor muscles activation,

followed by stabilization, suggesting an adaptive response, shaped by afferent feedback, Figures 3.9.

Finally, we stimulated the L4 site while varying the stimulation current to investigate the influence of proprioceptive feedback on motor-evoked responses. The presence of feedback attenuates the overall motor response and delays saturation as stimulation current increases. Furthermore at low stimulation levels, we observed bump-like activations, not present on the absence of proprioceptive feedback, as illustrated in Figures 3.10.

(a) Motoneuron activity, muscle activation, and ankle kinematics across different EES frequencies (current: 300 μ A, site S2).

(b) Impact of varying EES current amplitudes on motoneuron firing, muscle activation patterns, and ankle kinematics (frequency: 50 Hz, site S2).

Figure 3.8: Effect of the frequency and the current at site S2

increasing frequency (a) and current (b), both enhance muscle activation. However their effects differ in dynamics: high frequency leads to tonic, sustained muscle activation while high current results in rapid saturation of the response.

Figure 3.9: **Effect of varying EES frequencies at site S1 on motoneuron activity, muscle activation, and ankle kinematics**

Varying the frequency EES at spinal site S1, with a fixed current of $300 \mu\text{A}$ modulates the amplitude of flexor-extensor oscillations without altering their periodicity. While the period of the rhythmic pattern remains stable, higher EES frequencies lead to increased motoneuron recruitment, and motoneuron firing rate and stronger muscle activation, resulting in larger ankle movements.

After analysing the effect of the continuous stimulation, we further investigated the effects temporal modulation of EES frequency. Specifically, we focus on phase-specific EES frequency stimulation. We applied two distinct EES frequencies, one during the flexor phase (stance) and another during the extensor phase (swing) at the site S1. The simulations showed that reducing stimulation frequency during the extensor phase causes the extensor muscle to become less active, and similarly, lowering the EES frequency during the flexor phase decrease the flexor muscle activation. These simulations revealed that the effects of EES are phase-dependent. Moreover, phase-specific EES gradually and selectively influences the activity of extensor versus flexor muscles [34, 9], offering promising neuromodulation possibilities (see Figure 3.11).

(a) Effect of varying stimulation current at L4 (frequency : 50 Hz)

(b) Effect of varying stimulation current at L4 in the absence of sensory feedback, (frequency : 50 Hz)

Figure 3.10: Sensory feedback shapes EES-driven responses.

Sensory feedback reduces motoneuron firing rates and muscle activation amplitudes, leading to more modulated responses. It also induces low-frequency “bump” dynamics, absent without feedback.

Figure 3.11: **Modulation of the relative activation of the flexor versus the extensor** While flexor and extensor afferent receive same EES input (stimulation site S1, current: 300 μ A), higher-frequency stimulation during the extensor phase relative to the flexor phase increases extensor activation. This show that EES effects are phase dependent, and that the stimulation is integrated with the on-going movement phase.

3.2.4 Optimizing EES stimulation to restore walking

Finally, we exploit our closed-loop model and our results about stimulation site selectivity and phase-EES frequencies effects to test the benefits of optimized spatiotemporal stimulation for reproducing physiological muscle activation patterns during walking. We developed two optimizers that dynamically adjust stimulation frequencies at spinal sites L4 and S2 during the flexor (swing) and extensor (stance) phases, respectively, to promote more natural muscle activation patterns. First, the Muscle in Time dataset, containing OpenSim-simulated muscle activation data during walking, reveals low-level flexor (tibialis anterior) activity for approximately 65% of the cycle and high-amplitude extensor (medialis gastrocnemius) activation for the remaining 35%. We aimed to reproduce this characteristic unbalanced activation pattern between flexor and extensor muscles. As expected, the results show that the optimized stimulation frequency was lower during the flexor phase than during the extensor phase. Moreover this spatiotemporal stimulation strategy produces muscle activation patterns that more closely resemble natural locomotion, compared to a constant-frequency protocol that switches sites but uses the same frequency for both phases: optimized strategy achieved a 50% improvement in RMSE compared to constant 40 Hz stimulation, as illustrated in Figure 3.12.

(a) Muscle activation comparison

(b) RMSE comparison: baseline vs. optimized

Figure 3.12: **Optimization of muscle activations using phase-specific EES.** (a) On the left, reference, optimized, and baseline muscle activations are shown over a single gait cycle. On the right, the corresponding stimulation frequencies for the optimized and baseline conditions are displayed. (b) RMSE comparison between optimized and baseline conditions.

Chapter 4

Discussion

4.1 Mechanisms of clonus generation

4.1.1 Clonus modeling

Our computational model successfully reproduced key features of ankle clonus using a simple monosynaptic reflex loop. Lowering the motoneuron firing threshold led to synchronous motoneuron firing and self-sustained rhythmic activity at approximately 5 Hz, closely aligning with clinically observed clonus frequencies [7], Figure 3.1. These oscillations persisted for more than ten cycles, consistent with the clinical definition of sustained clonus [53]. Notably, the first oscillation period was longer, followed by progressive shortening and stabilization around the fourth or fifth cycle, an evolution pattern also observed in clinical data [7, 53].

Importantly, the emergence of these pathological oscillations occurred without invoking a central pattern generator (CPG), supporting the hypothesis that increased reflex gain alone is sufficient to generate clonus [20].

4.1.2 Origin of clonus following SCI

Our closed-loop model supports the hypothesis that clonus primarily results from increased motoneuron excitability. This hyper-excitability arises from the disruption of supraspinal inhibitory control and subsequent maladaptive reorganization of spinal reflex circuits following SCI [27]. The loss of descending modulation impairs both pre- and postsynaptic inhibition, leading to heightened reflex gain and exaggerated responses to sensory input.

Under physiological conditions, the soleus reflex demonstrates low-frequency-dependent post-activation depression (LFD), a protective mechanism that reduces motoneuron excitability with repeated activation. In chronic SCI, this mechanism is significantly impaired, resulting in increased responsiveness of the soleus (SOL) motoneurons even to minimal afferent input [27].

4.2 Bi-muscle model: impact of parameters variations

Sensitivity analysis revealed that key parameters such as the spike threshold potential, inhibitory reversal potential, and resting membrane potential strongly influence ankle movement. Fortunately, these are typically well constrained by biological data. In contrast, afferent connections showed particularly high sensitivity, likely due to their upstream role in the network. As downstream synapses are more distributed and possibly compensatory, early connections exert greater influence, underscoring the critical role of afferent input in shaping network dynamics, Figure 3.2.

With carefully tuned parameters, our model predicts rhythmic alternation between flexor and extensor activation under epidural stimulation at the S1 site. However, small variations in parameters can trigger bifurcations, shifting the network into regimes of alternation, dominance, or co-activation. For instance, minor changes in the synaptic time constant τ_i led to qualitatively distinct behaviors, Figure 3.3.

We used $\tau_i = 2.5$ ms, a standard value in the Brian2 community for fast synapses such as AMPA [44]. Still, experimental validation is needed, as real motor outputs under EES may involve co-activation or sustained activation rather than strict alternation.

4.3 Essential mechanisms for locomotor like flexor/extensor alternation pattern

One of the main findings of our closed-loop model is that locomotor-like dynamics can emerge purely from neuromuscular feedback, without requiring the assumption of a central pattern generator. Our simulations revealed two fundamental mechanisms required for generating physiological rhythmic patterns of muscle activation: reciprocal inhibition and proprioceptive feedback loops.

4.3.1 Reciprocal inhibition

Reciprocal inhibition ensures that activation of one muscle leads to inhibition of its antagonist through inhibitory interneurons that suppress opposing motoneuron activity. This circuit architecture prevents simultaneous co-activation of agonist and antagonist muscles, enabling alternating contractions essential for coordinated movement.

SCI disrupts rhythm generating mechanisms, particularly by reducing reciprocal Ia inhibition and inducing abnormal spinal sprouting, both of which contribute to muscle co-contraction [6]. Clinical studies report increased co-activation in patients with impaired reciprocal inhibition, especially during rapid movements, underscoring the role of inhibitory dysfunction in pathological motor patterns [6]. Further simulations with weakened reciprocal inhibition under EES are needed to better characterize the EES effects in individuals with SCI.

4.3.2 The role of proprioceptive feedback

The second mechanism involves feedback loops mediated by proprioceptive afferents. The muscle state influences the afferent firing rates, which serve as input to the spinal neuronal network; in turn, the output of this neuronal network activates the muscles and alters their state, completing a self-sustaining feedback loop. More precisely, muscle contraction reduces muscle length, decreasing Ia and II afferent firing rates and diminishing excitatory input to motoneuron. Simultaneously, increased tendon tension elevates Ib afferent activity, providing additional inhibitory input that facilitates the transition to antagonist muscle activation. Once the movement initiated, proprioceptive feedback drives the alternating pattern (rhythms generation before stabilization) through modulation of reciprocal inhibitory circuits, creating sustained oscillatory behavior, Figure 3.5.

The role of proprioceptive feedback goes beyond generating flexor/extensor alternation. We showed that proprioception feedback shape motor output and lead to adaptive response by limiting for instance muscle over-excitation. Additionally, we observed that proprioception feedback tend to promote bumps type dynamics at low intensity of stimulation, resembling those reported by Minassian et al. [32] during stepping-like movements under EES. In our model, these unsustained contraction of the tibialis anterior appear to result from transient stretch reflexes, triggered by passive ankle plantarflexion in the musculoskeletal model due to insufficient input, Figure 3.10.

4.4 EES modulate proprioceptive feedback

As we have seen, proprioceptive feedback is critical for regulating motor output and enable locomotor recovery after spinal cord injury (SCI)[47]. EES utilizes sensory feedback by activating afferent fibers for motor pattern generation [34], and as consequence understanding how EES modulate proprioceptive feedback to shape motor response is fundamental. Our findings suggest that aligning EES bursts with the natural timing of proprioceptive feedback is essential for preserving sensory dynamics during locomotion.

As expected, our simulations demonstrate that unbalanced afferent recruitment between the flexor and the extensor lead to preferential activation of one muscle group over another. Specifically, unbalanced continuous EES interferes with the typical increase in antagonist afferent firing that follows agonist contraction by preferentially enhancing agonist afferent activity. This effect maintains activation of the same muscle. Unbalanced recruitment of afferents promote selectivity and precise activation of individual muscles, which is valuable for developing targeted motor control therapies. This is particularly possible in lower limb applications, where spinal motor roots exhibit superior selectivity compared to cervical segments [18].

Conversely, balanced recruitment of flexor and extensor afferent by EES (S1), preserve proprioceptive information and induces stable alternating activation patterns at approximately 2.5 Hz, Figure 3.6. However, in SCI patients exhibiting reduced reciprocal inhibition, continuous EES at the S1 site may lead to undesired co-activation of flexor and extensor muscles, as illustrated in Figure 3.7. In such cases, a spatiotemporal EES protocol that mimics natural proprioceptive firing patterns would likely be more effective. By reproducing

time-dependent afferent activity, this approach could reinforce reciprocal inhibition, reduce co-activation, and enhance the efficacy of locomotor recovery. Further simulations are required to validate this hypothesis.

4.5 Value of the closed-loop model

4.5.1 Modeling SCI effects

Our model effectively captures the consequences of neuronal disinhibition commonly observed in SCI patients. For instance, increased motoneuron firing thresholds can lead to pathological clonus oscillations 3.1, while reduced Ia reciprocal inhibition results in abnormal muscle co-activation patterns 3.7.

These case studies demonstrate how disinhibitory mechanisms following SCI shape motor output and EES effects.

Finally, given the critical influence of anatomical and spinal root variability across individuals, adjustments to recruitment curves can be incorporated to reflect subject-specific differences.

4.5.2 Design EES stimulation

Our closed-loop model enables the design and testing of various EES strategies by manipulating parameters such as stimulation frequency, current intensity, and electrode placement, (Figures 3.6, 3.8, and 3.9). Using this framework, our simplified EES model reveals that increasing either the stimulation frequency or current produces similar effects on the system. Notably, we assume that motoneurons are not directly recruited by EES. However, higher stimulation currents are likely to recruit additional fibers. When the current becomes strong enough to directly activate motoneurons, this may result in the simultaneous co-activation of both agonist and antagonist muscles.

Our closed-loop model allow us to test non continuous EES stimulation, such as applying different frequencies during the flexor and the extensor phases of the gait cycle Figure 3.11. Our results, supported experimentally [9], reveal that the spinal cord selectively filters EES inputs depending on the ongoing motor phase: while both flexor and extensor afferent are stimulated equally, the EES stimulation during the flexor phase impact only the flexor and not the extensor. Turning off the stimulation during the extensor phase produce no activation at all of the extensor. This demonstrates that the spinal circuitry dynamically integrates EES input with endogenous motor activity. Phase-specific EES frequencies thus represent a promising strategy for restoring balanced flexor/extensor activation, forming a neurophysiological basis for the development of temporally patterned EES therapies.

Additionally, our closed-loop model enables the optimization of spatiotemporal EES protocols to more closely replicate natural muscle activation patterns during locomotion, Figure 3.12. While the generated activity does not yet perfectly replicate physiological patterns, these results highlight the potential of phase-specific and spatially targeted EES for promoting more naturalistic walking restoration.

Chapter 5

Conclusions

5.1 Summary

In this study, we addressed a key limitation of the model developed by Moraud et al. [34], which required the injection in the model of pre-recorded kinematic data during walking. Their approach relied on offline experimental data from rats, limiting its applicability to novel or dynamic conditions. In contrast, our model integrates proprioceptive feedback computed directly from muscle output calculated with Opensim. By doing so, our model is self-contained, gain predictive capabilities, and demonstrate how the dynamics emerge from the interplay between muscles and neural spinal network. This extension enables the analysis of two case studies, ankle clonus and EES-evoked multi-muscle activity, highlighting both pathological oscillations in SCI and the role of EES in modulating proprioceptive feedback and shaping motor output. These studies demonstrate the flexibility of our pipeline across varying neural complexities and stimulation modalities, offering mechanistic insights from pathological rhythmicity to functional recovery. The clonus model reveals reflex driven oscillations, while the bimuscle model informs EES based neuromodulation strategies, supporting the development of improved therapies for SCI.

5.2 Model limitations

Our current model has several limitations. In this section, we highlight some of the main constraints of the closed-loop framework.

5.2.1 EES-afferents coupling model

First, our EES-afferents coupling model likely overestimates post-EES firing rates. Simple calculations based on Poisson processes show that, with a baseline firing rate of 20 Hz and an EES frequency of 80 Hz, the resulting mean afferent firing rate would reach approximately 83 Hz (see Appendix), which is unrealistically high. In humans, afferent firing rates above 50 Hz are rarely observed [50].

5.2.2 Frequency of the flexor/extensor alternation

The oscillation frequency between extensor and flexor muscles produced by our model (2-3 Hz) exceeds typical biological rhythms pattern (~ 1 Hz). Increasing the reaction time to 300 ms brought the frequency closer to human gait patterns (Figure 3.4b), suggesting that the original reaction time may have been underestimated or that the muscle spindle model lacks human specificity.

Indeed, although baseline firing rates were rescaled, the muscle spindle model, originally derived from cat data, may not accurately reflect human physiology. Several alternative, more biophysically detailed models have been proposed [38, 30, 12, 5, 4], which could improve physiological accuracy. Future work should incorporate human specific spindle models to better reproduce realistic flexor/extensor alternation frequencies.

5.2.3 Synaptic connection parameters

The reciprocal inhibitory network comprises many synaptic parameters, such as synaptic weights and connectivity patterns. However, the precise architecture of spinal circuits and the exact values of these parameters remain largely unknown. Our simulations suggest that the synaptic weight between Ia/II afferents and reciprocal inhibitory interneurons may be overestimated, as these interneurons show higher firing rates compared to others. Moreover, variability in neuronal connectivity across patients further complicates the accurate specification of parameter values in computational models.

5.2.4 Ground reaction forces

The current closed-loop model does not incorporate ground reaction forces, which limits its ability to accurately reproduce gait dynamics, especially at the ankle joint. Including these forces in future simulations is essential to achieve more realistic and biomechanically accurate representations of gait kinematics.

5.3 Future work

Our current clonus model is relatively simple and simulates only a single muscle. However, muscles such as the tibialis anterior also play a critical role in the duration and dynamics of ankle clonus. Impaired reciprocal inhibition between the tibialis anterior and soleus muscles can lead to abnormal co-activation, which may favor the sustained oscillations observed in clonus [49, 6]. Clonus is more likely to persist when local circuits are activated in isolation without opposition from antagonist muscles [49]. Using our reciprocal inhibitory network to model clonus could yield new insights into how reduced Ia reciprocal inhibition contributes to its emergence. Wallace et al. showed that clonus duration decreased when three or four ipsilateral muscles were activated, and was shortened even further by contralateral muscle activation [49]. This highlights the importance of modeling multi-muscle dynamics in capturing clonus behavior. Moreover, simulations that include EES could be interesting in order to understand how EES may reduce reflex hyper excitability in individuals with spinal cord injury [33].

In the context of Case Study 2, future simulations should incorporate ground reaction forces to optimize the spatiotemporal parameters of EES stimulation for restoring walking.

Chapter 6

Appendix

6.1 EES-afferent coupling overestimates post-stimulation firing rates

The EES-afferent coupling model used in the present study tends to overestimate afferent firing rates after epidural electrical stimulation, producing unrealistically high values. This section explains this limitation with simple calculations showing how the model's output depends on the pre-EES firing rate and stimulation frequency, in the approximation of static afferent firing rate.

6.1.1 Poisson process

Assume a constant afferent firing rate r , and suppose that the number of spike events in a time interval follows a homogeneous Poisson process. The probability that exactly m spikes occur within an interval of length Δt is given by:

$$P(m \text{ spikes during } \Delta t) = \frac{e^{-r\Delta t}(r\Delta t)^m}{m!}$$

where r is the mean firing rate (in Hz).

6.1.2 Waiting time between spikes

Given any time t_0 , what is the probability that the next spike occurs after a delay τ ?

$$P(\text{next spike occurs after } \tau) = P(0 \text{ spikes during } \tau) = e^{-r\tau}$$

$$P(\text{next spike occurs before } \tau) = 1 - P(\text{next spike occurs after } \tau) = 1 - e^{-r\tau}$$

This is precisely the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of an exponential distribution. Therefore, the inter-spike interval (ISI) follows an exponential distribution.

6.1.3 Refractory period consideration

The mean of an exponential distribution with rate parameter r is:

$$\mathbb{E}[\text{ISI}] = \frac{1}{r}$$

If we introduce an absolute refractory period τ_{ref} , during which no spikes can occur, the mean interval between two spikes becomes:

$$\mathbb{E}[\text{ISI}] = \frac{1}{r} + \tau_{\text{ref}}$$

Translating this expression in terms of the effective firing rate ν , we get:

$$\nu = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{r} + \tau_{\text{ref}}}$$

Now, suppose r is the sum of the baseline afferent firing rate (f_{base}) and the stimulation frequency (f_{EES}):

$$r = f_{\text{base}} + f_{\text{EES}}$$

Then the effective afferent firing rate ν after EES is:

$$\nu = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{f_{\text{base}} + f_{\text{EES}}} + \tau_{\text{ref}}}$$

Numerical example Consider the following parameters:

- Baseline Ia afferent firing rate: $f_{\text{base}} = 20$ Hz
- Stimulation frequency: $f_{\text{EES}} = 80$ Hz
- Absolute refractory period: $\tau_{\text{ref}} = 2$ ms = 0.002 s

Then:

$$\nu = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{100} + 0.002} = \frac{1}{0.01 + 0.002} = \frac{1}{0.012} \approx 83.3 \text{ Hz}$$

This resulting effective firing rate of approximately 83 Hz is quite high, especially for humans, where afferent firing rates typically do not exceed 50 Hz [16]. Further biological experiments and more sophisticated computational models are necessary to fully characterize this nonlinear coupling.

6.2 Code availability

The code for this project is available upon request at <https://github.com/MathieuCharbonnier/EES-Spinal-Flow-Modulation/tree/main>, subject to access permissions. To request access, please send an email to mathieu.charbonnier@epfl.ch. All figures in this thesis are fully reproducible using the dedicated notebook `figures.ipynb`. Additionally, an `example.ipynb` notebook is provided to guide users on how to use the pipeline.

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